

Lagrangian and Fisher Information Variations and Pressure

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It is well known that a Lagrangian (usually kinetic energy - potential) may be varied to produce Newton's second law of motion. In (1) it is noted that kinetic energy is proportional to a Fisher's information of the form $b \int dt dx/dt dx/dt$ ($b=\text{constant}$) and so in a sense Fisher's information may be varied together with another piece i.e. $-V(x)$. In (2), it is noted that Fisher's information, this time with a probability $P(x)$, i.e. $b \int dx P(x) \{d/dx \ln(P)\} \{d/dx \ln(P)\}$ may be varied (with constraints) to yield the Schrodinger equation. (One may note that the two definitions of Fisher's information are the same if $P(x)=x(t)x(t)$ in the first case.)

Here we consider the notion of impulse and pressure which depends on p . We argue that a free quantum particle with constant p undergoes $x=p/m t$ on average, but is associated with a probability distribution $\exp(ipx)$ which contains uncertainty in x (within a wavelength) and no time. P , however, represents an impulse which the particle may impart. In the case of potential $V(x)$ one may consider a linear (interfering) sum of $\exp(ipx)$'s i.e. $W(x)=$ wavefunction = Sum over p $a(p)\exp(ipx)$. This leads to an average impulse of $\langle p \rangle = -i dW/dx / W$. Classically pressure is created by multiplying impulse by velocity (flux). If time does not exist within a wavelength then there is no time within it. There is, however, still an external clock and p ave in a sense should correspond to an $m v(\text{ave})$ nonrelativistically. Thus $\langle p \rangle \langle p \rangle WW$ (bound system) is in a sense like a pressure. One may then suggest that for an equilibrium scenario one extremizes this pressure with respect to constraints (EW and $V(x)W$). The variation is with respect to $W(x)$, the wavefunction. Given that a bound particle maps to an rms momentum such that $KE(x) = p_{rms}(x)p_{rms}(x)/2m$ where $p_{rms}(x)$ is the classical value, then at the classical level $p_{rms}(x) v_{rms}(x)$ should be pressure and should also satisfy an extremization equation. In fact, the extremization equation using $\langle p \rangle \langle p \rangle WW$ should be very closely related to it. One is in fact the d/dx of the other. The classical notion of pressure, proportional to vv , may be extremized subject to constraints. This leads to Newton's second law which contains d/dt explicitly. Changing to "x" concepts yields $v(x)d/dx$ which may be integrated to yield an energy conservation equation matching the quantum one.

Thus we try to think of extremization of Fisher's information i.e. EPI (extreme physical information) in terms of pressure, in both the classical and quantum cases.

Fisher's Information

Fisher's information is a statistical quantity given by:

$$I = \int dx P(x) \{ d/dx \ln(P) \} \{ d/dx \ln(P) \} \quad ((1))$$

If $P(x) = q(x)q(x)$ then ((1)) is equivalent to:

$$I = \int dx dq/dx dq/dx \quad ((2))$$

In the case of quantum mechanics, one may use the form ((1)), while for classical mechanics one may change the variable x to t and use ((2)).

Variation of a Lagrangian (1)

A Lagrangian is usually given by:

$$L = T - V(x) \text{ where } T = \frac{m}{2} \frac{dx}{dt} \frac{dx}{dt} \quad ((3))$$

Thus T is of the form of Fisher's information (multiplied by $m/2$) with the constraint $-V(x)$. Varying leads to Newton's second law:

$$\frac{d}{dt} mv = -dV/dx \quad ((4))$$

This may in turn be integrated to yield:

$$m \frac{dv}{dx} = -dV/dx \rightarrow \frac{m}{2} v^2 + V(x) = E \quad ((5))$$

Variation of Fisher's Information and Quantum Mechanics (2)

Using (1) (multiplied by a constant) together with a constraint $\int P(x) dx = 1$ and another $V(x)P(x)$, one may perform a variation of $P(x)$ to obtain an equation in $P(x)$ i.e. (see (2))

$$\frac{1}{P} \frac{dP}{dx} \frac{dP}{dx} + \frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{2}{P} \frac{dP}{dx} \right) + V(x) = E \quad ((6))$$

Using $P=W$ leads to the Schrodinger equation: $-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} + V(x) = E \quad ((7))$

As a result, the same kind of variational approach linked to Fisher's information (multiplied by a constant) together with some constraints applies in both the classical and quantum cases. The constraints are also similar in that $V(x)$ is used in both cases.

Difference Between the Fisher's Extremization for the Classical and Quantum Cases

It may be noted that even though the Fisher's extremization approaches (EPI) for the classical and quantum cases are very similar, there is a difference. The classical case retains the idea of two variables x, t , while the quantum only uses x . Secondly, the constraints differ. The classical case only uses a $V(x)$ constraint, while the quantum case explicitly uses $\int P(x) dx = 1$. Furthermore, the classical case, i.e. Newton's second law, must be integrated to obtain the form: $\frac{p(x)p(x)}{2m} + V(x) = E$. The integrated form follows by moving from an $x-t$ picture to a $p(x) - x$ picture i.e. removing time. The quantum case has already removed time and is in a form containing E .

Pressure and the Idea of Extremization?

As noted above, the statistical quantity Fisher's information, may be extremized, subject to constraints, to yield not only classical mechanics, but quantum mechanics as well. We ask: Is there a way to explain this physically?

We note that in the classical case, Fisher's information is proportional to mvv which is proportional to classical pressure with mv being an impulse and v a flux. Thus one may think of the variation as linked to pressure which has a physical meaning.

What about the quantum mechanical case? A free quantum particle has a constant p and moves as $x=p/m t$ (nonrelativistically). Matters, however, are more complicated because the particle is associated with a square root type probability $\exp(ipx)$ which contains two spatial probability distributions $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$. $P(x) = \exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = 1$ as every x point has the same weight. There are, however, two probability distributions in x which associate physically with the impulse represented by p . Thus on average the particle moves deterministically as $x=p/m t$, but internally there is no time and one thinks in terms of impulse.

In the case of a potential $V(x)$, one may think in terms of a linear superposition of $\exp(ipx)$ i.e.:

$$W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((8))$$

As a result, an average impulse may be given by:

$$\text{Average impulse} = -idW/dx / W \quad ((9))$$

If one thinks classically in terms of an average velocity associated with this average impulse, then: $v(\text{ave})$ is proportional to $-idW/dx / W$ as well. Furthermore in a bound system there is a physical density $W(x)W(x)$. Putting these together creates the classical type object:

$$\text{Average pressure} = W(x)W(x) (-dW/dx / W) (-dW/dx / W) = dW/dx dW/dx \quad ((10))$$

One should note that the average velocity associated with $dW/dx / W$ is not the classical v , as we will show.

One may now consider two constraints, one associated with $\text{Integral } W(x)W(x) dx = 1$ and another with $V(x) W(x)W(x)$ (the average potential energy). Finally one may vary ((10)) (multiplied by $1/(2m)$) with respect to these two constraints to obtain the Schrodinger equation.

$$-1/2m d/dx dW/dx + V(x) = E_n \quad ((11))$$

The classical velocity $v(x)$ (which maps somehow to the quantum case) also leads to a similar equation. Again $v(x)v(x)$ is proportional to pressure so one has:

$$d/dt m v(x) = -dV/dx \quad ((12))$$

((11)) contains only x , but ((12)) contains x, t so one must try to remove the explicit presence of t i.e.:

$$dp/dx \quad p/m = -dV/dx \rightarrow \text{integrate} \rightarrow \quad pp/2m + V(x) = E \quad ((13))$$

Thus ((11)) and ((13)) are the same, but v classical is associated with a $v_{rms}(x)$ in the quantum picture given by $\sqrt{2m(-1/2m d/dx dW/dx)}$.

Thus the classical notion of pressure, and its use in a variational principle, appears both in the classical formulation and the quantum formulation (which uses $\text{density} = W(x)W(x)$ which is already using classical notions). For a given wavefunction $W(x)$, one may think only in terms of impulse with time being removed. The Schrodinger equation, however, implicitly contains time through $KE(x)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that Fisher's information, a statistical quantity, may be extremized through EPI (2) to obtain both the classical result (extremizing a Lagrangian) or Schrodinger's equation. We argue that a classical notion of pressure is proportional to Fisher's information in both cases, i.e. v classically and $W(x)W(x) (-idW/dx / W) (-idW/dx / W)$ quantum mechanically. The quantum mechanical expression makes use of a classical form i.e. pressure, but that is fine, we argue, because $W(x)$ represents the quantum square root probability, but if one writes expressions using $P(x) = W(x)W(x)$, one is thinking in classical terms. (Ultimately, however, $W(x)$ governs everything).

Thus in both cases, one may extremize pressure and obtain two equations which essentially map into each other. The classical v leads to Newton's second law which contains an explicit time dependent: d/dt . Writing this as $v d/dx$ and integrating yields a conservation of energy equation. Extremizing pressure $W(x)W(x) (-idW/dx / W) (-idW/dx / W)$ subject to the constraint $P(x)$ and $V(x)P(x)$ leads to Schrodinger's equation which only contains x and already has E present. The two equations thus are essentially the same and both are linked to the physical notion of extremizing pressure subject to constraints.

References

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